

A Comprehensive Literature Review: Exploring the Indian Ancient Education System and NEP 2020 and Their Impact on the Contemporary Indian Education System

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Received : 20/08/2024

1st BPR : 27/08/2024

2nd BPR : 02/09/2024

Accepted : 10/09/2024

Abstract

From the Vedic era to the medieval era, India's educational heritage has been shaped by the Guru-Shishya tradition and comprehensive pedagogy, which have fostered intellectual curiosity, moral values, and cultural resilience. Generations of scholars and visionaries were influenced by establishments such as Takshashila, Nalanda, and Gurukuls. NEP 2020 represents a paradigm shift in education, emphasizing digital integration, multilingualism, adaptable curriculum frameworks, and basic literacy as means of developing 21st-century abilities. The influence of NEP 2020 and traditional Indian education on the current Indian educational system is critically examined in this paper. While India's ancient educational system placed a strong emphasis on moral values and community involvement, NEP 2020 is in line with modern problems, technical developments, and international objectives, adding to the country's rich and prestigious educational landscape.

Key words: Ancient Education in India, Higher Education, National Education Policy (NEP) 2020.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. ANCIENT INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

Indian education has its origins in antiquity and is distinguished by a wide range of educational establishments, pedagogical strategies, and intellectual foundations. India has a long history of education and learning dating back to ancient times. These were passed down orally or in writing. The knowledge, customs, and practices that shaped and uplifted humanity were thought to have originated from the ancient educational system of India. The foundation of the ancient Indian educational system, which dates back thousands of years, were Gurukuls, or residential schools in which pupils or learners resided with their tutors, or gurus, and got lessons in a range of subjects, including astronomy, mathematics, philosophy, Vedic scriptures, and ethics. In addition to academic knowledge, character development, moral principles, and the nurturing of qualities, attributes, values, and characteristics were all stressed in ancient Indian education.

The Gurukul tradition is the foundation of the ancient Indian education system, providing an abundance of knowledge and wisdom. Gurukuls functioned as educational hubs where students not only learned academic courses but also absorbed qualitative life values and moral principles from respected gurus. This antiquated system, which is captured in books like the Upanishads and Arthashastra, laid the groundwork for a distinctive educational philosophy that emphasized the combination of mental, ethical, and religious elements as well as the links between various fields. Both formal and informal educational systems were in place in ancient India. Education was given at gurukuls, pathshalas, temples, and at homes in ancient times. Students gained more knowledge about the environment and existence, as well as customs, religion, dharma, honesty, discipline, and

independence or self-reliance. The cornerstones or key elements of the ancient Indian educational system included life knowledge, students' holistic and all-around development, focus on oral learnings, social work development, and vocational training.

Ancient Indian education progressed over several periods. During the Vedic period, religious writings were memorized and recited in gurukuls. The founders of Buddhism and Jainism, Gautama Buddha and Mahavira, respectively, placed a strong emphasis on the value of education and analytical thinking. In viharas and stupas, Buddhism and Jainism both stressed analytical thought. Sanskrit was the medium of language during the Vedic system, while in the Buddhist system it was Pali. (Mangesh M. Ghonge, 2020)

Takshashila and other prominent universities flourished throughout the Mauryan Empire, while Nalanda rose to prominence during the Gupta dynasty. Founded in 700 B.C., Takshashila was the world's first university. Takshashila University was well-known for its medical programs and for having a stellar faculty that included renowned grammarian Panini, Chandragupta Maurya's minister Kautilya (Chanakya), and renowned medical instructor Charaka. (Dr. Rajashree, 2014) Whereas, Nalanda University, situated in modern-day Bihar, India, flourished as a Buddhist educational hub, drawing intellectuals from all around Asia. It provided a thorough education covering logic, Sanskrit literature, medicine, Buddhism, and other subjects.

Gurukuls and madrasas provided free education in medieval India; however, Western techniques were implemented during the colonial period, marginalizing local knowledge.

1.2 NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP) 2020

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a turning point in the history of education in India by providing a forward-thinking plan for reviving the system, encouraging creativity, and advancing all-encompassing growth. NEP 2020, which will serve as a revolutionary framework, displays a thorough comprehension of the evolving needs and aspirations of India's diverse population. The recommendations of an expert committee led by Dr. Kasturirangan, the former chairman of the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO), served as the foundation for the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. (P. S.& Shubhrajyotsna, 2020)

A series of public consultations ensued when the Ministry of Human Resource Development presented a Draft New Education Policy in 2019. Reducing curricular content is discussed in the Draft NEP as a way to improve critical thinking, essential learning, and more comprehensive experiential, discussion- and analysis-based learning. (Pawan Kalyani, 2020)

Key Highlights of NEP 2020:

- The 5+3+3+4 system will take the place of the outdated educational model of the 10+2 system.
- Internships and vocational education will begin in class six.
- Teaching in the native language or mother tongue up to at least Grade 5.
- Removal of the stream system. Students will now be able to select from a wider variety of subjects in different streams.
- To evaluate the pupils, the National Assessment Center, known as "PARAKH" (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic Development), has been established.
- To promote a robust research culture, the National Research Foundation will be founded.
- To make credit transfers easier, an academic bank of credits is going to be created.
- Students will go ten days a year without carrying a backpack.
- Twice a year, the National Testing Agency (NTA) will administer a common college entrance exam.
- Preferably, a four-year bachelor's degree in many disciplines.
- MPhil to be discontinued.

The NEP 2020 saw three key alterations, which were as follows:

- ✓ The HRD ministry was renamed the Ministry of Education.
- ✓ A minimum of 6% of GDP will be allocated to education, up from the current 1.6% level.

✓ Concentrating on the Gross Enrollment Ratio. By 2035, the goal is to raise it to 50%.

2. Review of Literature

Nandita and P.S. Aithal (2023)¹ carried out a study on the relevance and significance of Ancient Indian Education in the modern education system, relying on a comprehensive literature review. According to their findings, techniques like asana, mantra chanting, and meditation help reduce stress and improve learning. Higher education institutions, regulated by the AICTE and UGC, are incorporating similar approaches. Yoga programs that emphasize Universal Human Values (UHV) promote complete personality development. Traditional teaching tactics are the foundation of modern memory-building strategies such as logical procedures and periodic learning.

S. Gopalkrishnan (2023)² carried out an exploratory study on the origins and relevance of indigenous ancient Indian education knowledge (AIKS) systems. His findings underlined the necessity for additional investigation into the National Education Policy (NEP), highlighting its potential long-term influence on Indian education.

Dr. Pankaj & Dr. Ashish (2021)³ reviewed India's new education policy, using a conceptual debate to study the national educational policy framework, NEP 2020's higher education policy, and its comparison to previous policies. The study provides insights into the historical context of the education system, the benefits of the new education policy, and comparisons to present programs. Overall, the research identifies favorable aspects of the new policy framework.

Dr. Sujan Biswas (2021)⁴ examined the scope, challenges and opportunities of the Indian Knowledge System and NEP 2020. He stressed that adopting NEP 2020 has the potential to cause big changes in India's education sector. The policy seeks to eliminate educational gaps, ensure excellent education delivery, and solve pedagogical issues and structural inequities. NEP 2020 is touted as a pioneering plan that aims to educate students for the future and match the demands of a 21st-century India.

Mangesh et al. (2020)⁵ carried out a study to compare the benefits and drawbacks of education in the ancient, medieval, and modern periods. They found that modern university education lacks real-world applicability, focusing more on competition than practical skills. The authors urge a return to the holistic approach of ancient and medieval education, emphasizing practical knowledge, strong student-teacher relationships, and understanding student lifestyles. They propose establishing an education system that fosters holistic growth, prepares children for the future, and equips them to handle stress effectively.

Pawan (2020)⁶ conducted an empirical study on NEP 2020 focusing on the consequences for stakeholders and the Indian educational system. He concluded that although everyone would be impacted, kids and teachers would be most directly impacted. The objective of the Indian government's NEP 2020 project is to enhance the nation's educational framework. All stakeholders see the potential for future success in every facet of the policy.

P. S. Aithal & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal (2020)⁷ examined the objectives of the Indian National Education Policy 2020. The goal of the strategy is to improve higher education's quality, affordability, and accessibility by encouraging the private sector to participate and putting in place quality controls. Results point to a movement in Indian higher education toward approaches that are competency-centered, experiment-based, knowledge-focused, skills-oriented, and driven by research.

Dr. Rajashree (2014)⁸, examines the history of education in India and credits Macaulay's British model from the 20th century for the current system. Progress was hampered by British influence, which gave humanities precedence over science and technology. The Indian educational system is still developing despite of obstacles, trying to get better and be more in line with its long-term objectives.

3. Objective of The Study

The objective of this research paper is to undertake a thorough literature review of the ancient Indian education system, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, and the corresponding impacts on the present Indian education system.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study includes a thorough analysis of scholarly literature, research papers, books, policy documents, and historical writings about the ancient Indian education system, NEP 2020, and modern educational practices in India. Primary and secondary sources were gathered using relevant databases such as Google Scholar, Research Gate, Scopus Journal, Academia, and other educational periodicals.

5. FINDINGS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

- The ancient education system focused on holistic development, moral values, and experiential learning.
- The Gurukul tradition is a key component of traditional Indian education, distinguished by the teacher-student connection and comprehensive learning environment.
- In Gurukuls, students lived close to their gurus (teachers), learning not just academic knowledge but also moral principles, life skills, and cultural traditions. Gurukul education was immersive and participative, emphasizing oral transmission, memory, and practical application of information.
- Vedic learning forms the foundation of ancient Indian education.
- NEP 2020 is in line with India's commitment to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which include Goal 4: Quality Education.
- NEP 2020 was created through extensive stakeholder engagements, expert committee discussions, and public input systems.
- NEP 2020 stresses holistic development, including cognitive, socio-emotional, and physical elements of learning, which is consistent with the holistic ethos of India's historic education system.
- The NEP-2020 envisions a multidisciplinary education that aspires to develop humans' social, physical, intellectual, emotional, and moral qualities in an integrated manner.
- Both the Indian traditional education system and NEP 2020 emphasize the significance of ethical ideals, citizenship education, and social responsibility in developing responsible individuals who contribute to the common purpose.

6. Conclusion

The study of the Indian ancient education system, in conjunction with the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, has significant consequences for modern Indian education. Exploring traditional pedagogical methods and concepts from ancient India can incorporate holistic learning approaches into current educational processes. This integration stresses character development, morals, and values in addition to intellectual study. Insights from past systems and NEP 2020 may spark a move toward interdisciplinary learning, boosting students' full grasp of varied subjects and skill development. NEP 2020's emphasis on skill development and vocational education is consistent with the holistic nature of education in ancient Indian systems, which emphasizes practical skills and craftsmanship in addition to academic knowledge. Empowering teachers through professional development and flexibility is consistent with both historical and contemporary educational ideologies, resulting in improved teaching quality and student results. NEP 2020's emphasis on technology integration is consistent with the upgrading of educational systems. Insights from ancient and current traditions may inspire the integration of cutting-edge technologies to improve teaching and learning experiences. This evolution will likely influence curriculum design, teaching methodologies, assessment practices, and the overall learning experience for students across the country.

Modern Indian education is shaped by the combined influence of NEP 2020 and the antiquated Indian educational system. We can gain valuable insights into the transformational power of combining progressive policy measures with historical legacies by building a bridge between the past and present. Finally, examining NEP 2020 and the historical Indian educational system encourages

self-examination, discussion, and coordinated efforts for inclusive, fair, equitable, and high-quality education in India. We pave the way for societal progress and educational enlightenment by accepting the past, appreciating the present, and looking to the future.

7. Limitations of the Study

- i. One drawback of this literature review is the scope of the sources examined. While we attempted to include a wide range of scholarly papers, books, and policy documents, some significant literature was probably ignored or excluded.
- ii. Another limitation is the time limit associated with performing a literature review. Due to time constraints, it may not have been able to thoroughly cover all historical periods and policy events about the Indian education system.
- iii. The literature studied may be skewed toward English-language sources, leaving out crucial insights from regional or native language publications and non-Western views.

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